

Suki and tobacco use
among the iTaukei
people of Fiji:
Bibliography

Centre of Research Excellence:
Indigenous Sovereignty & Smoking

Suki and tobacco use among the iTaukei people of Fiji: Bibliography

About 5 per cent (about 350 million) of the world's population is recognized as indigenous and smoking prevalence is disproportionately higher among many Indigenous peoples. There is a lack of research on smoking prevalence and cessation behavior among most of these indigenous groups. Further, where research exists, the results suggest that existing tobacco control programmes have not been as effective for indigenous people. Understanding why this is so and identifying what else can be done to reduce smoking-related harm among indigenous people will contribute to reducing the inequities many indigenous people still experience.

The goal of the *Centre of Research Excellence: Indigenous Sovereignty & Smoking* is to advance knowledge on Indigenous tobacco use and how to more rapidly reduce smoking harm among Indigenous people worldwide.

We will do this by:

- Identifying Indigenous tobacco harm reduction strategies and interventions.
- Identifying strategies to support Indigenous tobacco smallholders to change their business model.
- Building the research capacity of Indigenous people so that they may devise their own culturally appropriate solutions to reduce the negative consequences of smoking.

Towards our goal we will compile a bibliography of all the literature we considered during the conduct of each study. After publication of the study report or journal articles, a PDF of the bibliography will be downloadable from our Centre website www.coreiss.com.

HOW TO USE THIS BIBLIOGRAPHY

When looking for a specific topic in the Bibliography, use the Find or 'Find on Page' function on your browser or use the keyboard shortcut 'Ctrl + F'. Then enter a keyword (e.g., suki) on the search bar and use the arrows or scroll down to scan through the whole document. The keyword will be highlighted where it is present.

The bibliography is sorted by the chapter headings used the study report. In this bibliography, sources are provided on the following topics:

- About Fiji
- iTaukei Health
- Suki and tobacco in Fiji
- Kava
- Tobacco Control

The *Suki and tobacco use among the iTaukei people of Fiji* report is available for download from our website: info@coreiss.com. On our website you can also register your email to receive notifications of new publications.

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About Fiji

- Apravasi Ghat Trust Fund. An overview of History of Indenture [Internet]. [place unknown]: Apravasi Ghat Trust Fund; [date unknown; cited 2019 June 11]. Available from: <http://www.apravasighat.org/English/Resources%20Research/Documents/History%20of%20Indenture.pdf>
- Appadurai A, Korom FJ, Mills MA. Gender, Genre, and Power in South Asian Expressive Traditions. Philadelphia: University of Pennsylvania Press; 2015. P. 363.
- Arno A. The World of Talk on a Fijian Island: An Ethnography of Law and Communicative Causation. [place unknown]: Ablex Publishing Corporation; 1993.
- Becker AE. Body, Self, and Society: The View from Fiji. Philadelphia: University of Pennsylvania Press; 1995.
- Belshaw CS. Under The Ivi Tree: Society and Economic Growth in Rural Fiji. London and New York: Routledge – Taylor and Francis Group; 2004. P. 31.
- Biturogoiwasa S, Walker AR. MY VILLAGE, MY WORLD: Everyday Life in Nadoria, Fiji. Suva, Fiji: Institute of Pacific Studies, The University of the South Pacific; 2001.
- Carter J. Pacific Islands Yearbook. 14th ed. Sydney: Pacific Publications; 1981. P. 272.
- Clunie F. Yalo i Viti: Shades of Viti: A Fiji Museum Catalogue. Suva, Fiji: Fiji Museum Suva; 1986.
- Connell J, Rugendyke B. Tourism at the Grassroots: Villagers and Visitors in the Asia-Pacific. Oxon: Taylor & Francis; 2008.
- Consumer Council of Fiji. Price of Cigarettes [press release] (2016 Jan 11) [cited 2019 July 23]. Available from: <http://www.consumersfiji.org/press-releases/pre/price-of-cigarettes>
- Derrick RA. The Fiji Islands: A Geographical Handbook. Suva, Fiji: Govt. Printing; 1951.
- Drescher S. The Historical Context of British Abolition. In: Richardson, D, London Frank Cass editors. Abolition and Its Aftermath: The Historical Context 1790–1916. London: Frank Cass; 2013.
- Fiji Bureau of Statistics. Statement on Ethnicity. Suva, Fiji: Fiji Bureau of Statistics; 2018; 16.
- Fiji Bureau of Statistics. Census of Population and Housing. Suva, Fiji: Fiji Bureau of Statistics; 2019.
- Ford CS. The Role of a Fijian Chief. Am Sociol Rev. 1938; 3: 541-50.
- France P. The Charter of the Land: Custom and Colonization in Fiji. Australia: Oxford University Press; 1969.
- Freeman JD, Geddes WR. Explanation of the Vanua and Matanitu. In: Anthropology in the South Seas: Essays presented to H.D. Skinner. [place unknown]: Thomas Avery and Sons; 1959. P. 210.

- Geddes WR. Deuba: a study of a Fijian village. Wellington, N.Z.: Polynesian society; 1945.
- Geraghty P, Mugler F, Tent J. Macquarie Dictionary of English for the Fiji Islands. [place unknown]: Macquarie Library; 2006.
- Geraghty PA. The History of the Fijian Languages. [place unknown]: University of Hawaii Press; 1983.
- Gharbaoui D, Blocher J. Limits to Adapting to Climate Change Through Relocations in Papua-New Guinea and Fiji. [place unknown]: Springer; 2017.
- Gillion K. Fiji's Indian migrants: a history of the end of indenture in 1920. Melbourne: Oxford U.P.; 1962.
- Govender V. Youth praise 1860 indentured labourers. 2016 08 [cited 2019 May 19]; Available from: <https://www.news24.com/SouthAfrica/Local/Coastal-Weekly/youth-praise-1860-indentured-labourers-20160907>
- Government of Fiji. Tobacco Control Decree 2010. Fiji: Government of Fiji; 2010. 31 p. Decree No.: 63.
- Haddon AC, Hornell J, Mulrooney M. Canoes of Oceania. [place unknown]: Bishop Museum Press; 1975.
- Hocart AM. Fijian Chiefs: A Recantation. Man. 1921; 21: 85-6.
- Hocart AM. Lau Islands, Fiji. Honolulu: Bernice P. Bishop Museum; 1929.
- Howard MC. Fiji: Race and Politics in an Island State. Vancouver: University of British Columbia; 1991.
- Kane HK. Voyagers. [place unknown]: WhaleSong; 1993.
- Kaplan M. Neither Cargo nor Cult: Ritual Politics and the Colonial Imagination in Fiji. Durham and London: Duke University Press; 1995.
- Katz R. The Straight Path: A Story of Healing and Transformation in Fiji. Canada: Addison-Wesley Publishing Company; 1994.
- Kelly JD. A Politics of Virtue: Hinduism, Sexuality and Countercolonial Discourse in Fiji. Chicago: University of Chicago Press; 1991.
- Kirch PV. The Lapita Peoples: Ancestors of the Oceanic World. [place unknown]: Blackwell Publishers; 1997.
- Knapman B. Economy and State in Fiji before and after the Coups. The Contemp Pacific. 1990; 2: 59-86.
- Lal BV. Broken Waves: A History of the Fiji Islands in the Twentieth Century. Honolulu: University of Hawaii Press; 1992.
- Lal BV. Fiji before the Storm: Elections and the politics of development. [place unknown]: ANU Press; 2012.
- Lal BV. Chalo Jahaji: On a journey through indenture in Fiji [Internet]. Division of Pacific and Asian History, RSPAS, ANU; 2012 [cited 2019 Mar 23]. Available from: <http://press-files.anu.edu.au/downloads/press/p212781/pdf/book.pdf?referer=123>
- Lal P. Decolonizing International Relations: A Re-Memory of Indentured Servitude in Fiji And How it Impacts Our Present and Future [Graduate Thesis]. Fiji: Fiji House of Representatives; 2000.

- Lal P, Lim-Applegate H, Reddy M. ALTA or NLTA: What's in the name? Land and Tenure Dilemma and the Fiji Sugar Industry. Land Tenure Center (Working Paper 46) Wisconsin-Madison: University of Wisconsin-Madison; 2001.
- Larmour P. Guarding the Guardians: Accountability and Anticorruption in Fiji's Cleanup Campaign. Honolulu, Hawaii, USA: East-West Center; 2008.
- Latourette KS. A History of the Expansion of Christianity. [place unknown]: Eyre and Spottiswoode; 1947.
- Lawson S. Fiji's foreign relations: Retrospect and Prospect. *The Commonwealth Journal of International Affairs*. 2015; 104: 209-20.
- Lin H-L. Vanua as Environment: Conservation, Farming, and Development in Waitabu, Fiji [PhD thesis]. [place unknown]: University of Pittsburgh; 2015.
- Macnaught TJ. The Fijian Colonial Experience: A study of the Neotraditional order under British colonial rule prior to World War II. Australia: The Australian National University; 1945.
- Mateiviti-Tulavu EK. Connecting Identities and Relationships through Indigenous Epistemology: The Solomoni of Fiji [PhD thesis]. Auckland, New Zealand: The University of Auckland; 2013.
- Mayer AC. Peasants in the Pacific: A Study of Fiji Indian Rural Society. [place unknown]: Routledge; 1961.
- McNamara KE, Westoby R. Ironies of globalisation: Observations from Fiji and Kiribati. *The Journal of Pacific Studies*. 2014; 34: 53-62.
- Miller K, Jones R, Pinheiro L. Fiji. [place unknown]: Lonely Planet; 2003.
- Ministry of Health. Non-Communicable Diseases Prevention and Control: National Strategic Plan 2010-2014. Fiji: Ministry of Health; [date unknown]. P. 32.
- Nabobo-baba U. Knowing and learning: an indigenous Fijian approach. Suva, Fiji: Institute of Pacific Studies, The University of the South Pacific; 2006.
- Nayacakalou RR. Leadership in Fiji. Melbourne: Oxford University Press; 1975.
- Nayacakalou RR. Tradition and change in the Fijian village. Suva, Fiji: South Pacific Social Sciences Association and the Institute of Pacific Studies, University of the South Pacific, Suva; 1978.
- Nicolas NPG. Planets around the sun: Dynamics and contradictions of the Fijian Matanitu (Oceania monographs). [place unknown]: University of Sydney; 1986.
- Norton RE. Race and Politics in Fiji. Queensland: University of Queensland Press; 1977.
- O'Sullivan D. Between Indigenous Paramountcy and Democracy: How Differentiated Citizenship and the UN Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples Could Help Fijian Self-determination. *Aust J Polit Hist*. 2018; 64: 129-41.
- Petrinovich L. The Cannibal Within. New York: Aldine De Gruyter; 2000. P. 135.
- Phillips T, Keen M. Sharing the City: Urban Growth and Governance in Suva, Fiji. SSGM Discussion Paper 2016/6. Canberra: The Australian National University; 2016.

- Quain B. *Fijian Village*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press; 1948.
- Rabuka SL. The Fiji islands in transition: personal reflections. In Lal B, *Fiji before the storm: Elections and the politics of development*. [place unknown]: ANU Press; 2012.
- Rai S. Girit Focus Articles. Australian newspaper Indian Links Girit Link. 2004 August. Available from: http://girit.org/?page_id=884
- Rakai ME, Ezigbalike IC, Williamson IP. Traditional Land Tenure Issues for Lis in Fiji. *Surv Rev*. 1995; 33: 247-62.
- Raven-Hart R. A Village In The Yasawas (Fiji). *The Journal of the Polynesian Society*. 1956; 65: 95–154.
- Ravuvu A. *Vaka i Taukei: The Fijian Way of Life*. 1st ed. [place unknown]: Institute of Pacific Studies of the University of the South Pacific; 1983.
- Routledge D. *Matanitu: The Struggle for Power in Early Fiji*. 1st ed. [place unknown]: University of the South Pacific; 1985.
- Sahlins MD. *Moala: Culture and Nature on a Fijian Island*. Ann Arbor: University of Michigan Press; 1962.
- Sahlins MD. *Apologies to Thucydides: Understanding History as Culture and Vice Versa*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press; 2004. P. 59.
- Schütz AJ, Komaitai RT. *Spoken Fijian: An Intensive Course in Bauan Fijian, with Grammatical Notes and Glossary*. [place unknown]: University of Hawaii Press; 1971.
- Schütz AJ. *The Fijian Language*. [place unknown]: University of Hawaii Press; 1985.
- Seeman B. *Viti: An account of a Government mission to the Vitian or Fijian Islands in the years 1860-61*. Cambridge: Macmillan & Co.; 1862.
- Sills J. “Stuck in Savusavu.” *Souled Outside* (blog), June 3, 2018. Available from: <http://souledoutblog.com/savusavu-delta-flights/>
- Singh S. Remembering Gandhi’s forgotten satyagraha to free bonded labourers from the British. *India*. 2017 March 28 [cited 2019 June 10]; *Daily O*.
- Talk Business. *Cash Crop Farming - Labasa, Fiji* [Internet]. Labasa, Fiji; 2013 [cited 2019 May 19]. Available from: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=LU2e3r_bfdc
- Tent J. A profile of the Fiji English lexis. *English World-Wide*. 2001; 22: 209-45.
- Thomas N. Sanitation and Seeing: The Creation of State Power in Early Colonial Fiji. *Comp Stud Soc Hist*. 1990; 32: 149-70.
- Thompson L. *Fijian Frontier*. [place unknown]: American Council, Institute of Pacific Relations; 1940.
- Toren C. *Making Sense of Hierarchy: Cognition as Social Process in Fiji*. London: The Athlone Press; 1990.
- Toren C. *Mind, Materiality and History*. 1st ed. [place unknown]: Routledge; 1999.
- Vanita. Girit 14 May 2014, it been 135 years, and we pay tribute to over 60,500* Giritiyas, of Fiji. 2014 May 14 [cited 2019 June 10]. Fiji. 2014. Available from: <http://girit.org/?p=1388>
- Watters RF. *Koro: Economic Development and Social Change in Fiji*. Oxford: Clarendon Press; 1969.

Williams T, Calvert J. *Fiji and the Fijians*. New York: D. Appleton and Company; 1859. P. 161-214.

Wright R. *On Fiji Islands*. Canada: Viking Penguin Inc.; 1986.

iTaukei Health

Asante AD, Irava W, Limwattananon S, et al. Financing for universal health coverage in small island states: Evidence from the Fiji Islands. *BMJ Global Health*. 2017; 2: 1-8.

Cambie RC, Ash J. *Fijian Medicinal Plants*. Csiro Publishing; 1994. P. 752.

Carter K, Cornelius M, Taylor R, et al. Mortality trends in Fiji. *Aust NZ Publ Heal*. 2011; 35: 412-20.

Cliff A, Haggett P, Ord J, et al.: *Spatial diffusion: an historical geography of epidemics in an island community*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press; 1981.

Cohen A, Brauer M, Burnett R, et al. Estimates and 25-year trends of the global burden of disease attributable to ambient air pollution: An analysis of data from the Global Burden of Diseases Study 2015. *The Lancet*. 2017; 389: 1907-18.

Connell J. 'The Fiji Times and the good citizen: constructing modernity and nationhood in Fiji'. *Contemp Pac*. 2007; 9: 85-109.

Countries and Their Cultures. Fiji [Internet]. [place unknown]: Countries and Their Cultures; [2019; cited date 2019 June 10]. Available from: <https://www.everyculture.com/Cr-Ga/Fiji.html>

Ellickson PL, Tucker JS, Klein DJ. High-risk behaviors associated with early smoking: Results from a 5-year follow-up. *J Adolescent Health: Official Publication of the Society for Adolescent Medicine* 2001; 28: 465-73.

Engelman D, Mataika L, Kado J, et al. Adherence to secondary antibiotic prophylaxis for patients with rheumatic heart disease diagnosed through screening in Fiji. *Trop Med Int Health*. 2016; 21: 1583-91.

Fiji Ministry of Health and Medical Services. *Fiji Adolescent Health Situational Analysis: 2016*. [place unknown]: Fiji Ministry of Health and Medical Services – 2016 October. 90 p. Version 20.

Flynn MG. Respiratory symptoms of rural Fijian and Indian children in Fiji. *Thorax*. 1994; 49: 1201-4.

GBD 2015 Healthcare Access and Quality Collaborators. Healthcare Access and Quality Index based on mortality from causes amenable to personal health care in 195 countries and territories, 1990-2015: a novel analysis from the Global Burden of Disease Study 2015. *The Lancet*. 2017; 390: 231-66.

Gyaneshwar R, Naidu S, Raban MZ, et al. Absolute cardiovascular risk in a Fiji medical zone. *BMC Public Health*. 2016; 16: 1-9.

Kaufman TM, Fazio S, Michael D, et al. Brief Commentary: Marijuana and Cardiovascular Disease—What Should We Tell Patients? *Ann Intern Med*. 2019; 170: 119-120.

Kessaram T, McKenzie J, Girin N, et al. Noncommunicable diseases and risk factors in adult populations of several Pacific Islands: Results from the

- WHO STEPwise approach to surveillance. *Aust N Z J Public Health*. 2015; 39: 336-43.
- Kessaram T, McKenzie J, Girin N, et al. Alcohol use in the Pacific region: Results from the STEPwise approach to surveillance, Global School-Based Student Health Survey and Youth Risk Behavior Surveillance System. *Drug Alcohol Rev* 2016; 35: 412-23.
- Khalif M. Global School-based Student Health Survey: Fiji Islands 2016 [Internet]. WHO South Pacific Office; 2016 [cited 2019 June 10]. Available from: https://www.who.int/ncds/surveillance/gshs/gshs_fs_fiji_2016.pdf
- Kispert S, Schwartz T, McHowat J. Cigarette Smoke Regulates Calcium-Independent Phospholipase A₂ Metabolic Pathways in Breast Cancer. *Am J Pathol*. 2017; 187: 1855-66.
- Lau CL, Watson CH, Lowry JH, et al. Human Leptospirosis Infection in Fiji: An Eco-epidemiological Approach to Identifying Risk Factors and Environmental Drivers for Transmission. *PLoS Negl Trop Dis*. 2016; 10: 1-25.
- Le Merchand L, Hankin JH, Bach F, et al. An ecological study of diet and lung cancer in the South Pacific. *Int J Cancer*. 1995; 63: 18-23.
- Leung CC, Yew WW, Chan CK, et al. Smoking adversely affects treatment response, outcome and relapse in tuberculosis. *Eur Respir J*. 2015; 45: 738-45.
- Ligairi J, Silatolu AM, Tukana I. NCD related deaths between 2012-2014: A retrospective descriptive study. *Fiji Journal of Public Health*. 2017; 6: 64-66.
- Linhart C, Tukana I, Lin S, et al. Continued increases in hypertension over three decades in Fiji, and the influence of obesity. *J Hypertens*. 2016; 34: 402-9.
- Linhart C, Tukana I, Lin S, et al. Declines and plateaux in smoking prevalence over three decades in Fiji. *Nicotine Tob Res*. 2017; 19: 1315-21.
- Mahesh PKB, Gunathunga MW, Jayasinghe S, et al. Breathing with an enemy in the kitchen: a narrative review of the concepts on cleaner energy, respiratory effects of indoor air pollution due to cooking and the potential way forward. *Journal of the College of Community Physicians of Sri Lanka*. 2018; 24: 2.
- Mannava P, Abdullah A, James C, et al. Health systems and noncommunicable diseases in the Asia-Pacific region: A review of the published literature. *Asia Pac J Public Health*. 2015; 27: 1-19.
- Melhado RE, Alderson D, Tucker O. The Changing Face of Esophageal Cancer. *Cancers*. 2010; 2: 1379-404.
- Ministry of Health and Medical Services, World Health Organisation, Fiji National University, et al. Fiji TB Manual. 4th Edition. [internet]. Fiji: Ministry of Health and Medical Services; 2017 [cited 11 June 2019]. Available from: <http://www.health.gov.fj/wp-content/uploads/2014/09/FIJI-TB-MANUAL-2017.pdf>
- Ministry of Health for the Alcohol Advisory Council of New Zealand Research (ALAC). Na tabili kavoro: The place of alcohol in the lives of Fijian people living in Aotearoa New Zealand. Sector Analysis (Wellington); 1997. Report No.: 4.

- Patel R, Huggard P, van Toledo A. Occupational Stress and Burnout among Surgeons in Fiji. *Front Public Health*. 2017; 5: 1-6.
- Phillips T, McMichael C, O’Keefe M. “We invited the disease to come to us”: neoliberal public health discourse and local understanding of non-communicable disease causation in Fiji. *Crit Public Health*. 2017; 28: 560-72.
- Pollaers K, Kujan O, Johnson NW, et al. Oral and oropharyngeal cancer in Oceania: Incidence, mortality, trends and gaps in public databases as presented to the Global Oral Cancer Forum. *Transl Res Oral Oncol*. 2017; 2: 1-8.
- Puamau ES, Roberts G, Schmich L, et al. Drug and Alcohol Use in Fiji: A Review. *Pac Health Dialog*. 2011; 17: 165-71.
- Queensland Health. The health of Queensland’s Fijian population 2009. Brisbane: Division of the Chief Health Officer, Queensland Health; 2011.
- Quinn J. Reducing drug harm in Fiji. *Matters of Substance*. 2012 May; 22: 2. Available from: <https://www.drugfoundation.org.nz/matters-of-substance/may-2012/reducing-drug-harm-in-fiji/>
- Ravuvu A, Friel S, Thow AM, et al. Protocol to monitor trade agreement food-related aspects: the Fiji case study. *Health Promot Int*. 2017; 33: 1-14.
- Schmic L, Power R. Situational analysis of drug and alcohol issues and responses in the Pacific 2008-09. Canberra: Australian National Council on Drugs; 2010.
- Sinclair R, Millar L, Allender S, et al. The Cross-Sectional Association between Diet Quality and Depressive Symptomology amongst Fijian Adolescents. *PLoS ONE*. 2016; 11: 1-12.
- Snowdon W, Raj A, Waqa G, et al. Non-communicable diseases and health system responses in Fiji. Fiji: Pacific Research Centre for the Prevention of Obesity and Non-Communicable Diseases, College of Medicine Nursing and Health Sciences, Fiji National University; 2013. Working Paper Series, No. 34.
- Striegel RH, Becker AE, Roberts AL, et al. Youth health-risk behaviour assessment in Fiji: The reliability of Global School-based Student Health Survey content adapted for ethnic Fijian girls. *Ethn Health*. 2010; 15: 181-97.
- Taylor R, Lin S, Linhart C, et al. Overview of trends in cardiovascular and diabetes risk factors in Fiji. *Ann Hum Biol*. 2018; 45: 188-201.
- Tolley H, Snowdon W, Wate J, et al. Monitoring and accountability for the Pacific response to the non-communicable diseases crisis. *BMC Public Health*. 2016; 16: 1-12.
- U.S. Department of Health and Human Services. Preventing Tobacco Use Among Youth and Young Adults: A Report of the Surgeon General. Atlanta, GA: U.S. Department of Health and Human Services, Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, National Center for Chronic Disease Prevention and Health Promotion, Office on Smoking and Health; 2012.
- Waqa G, Bell C, Snowdon W, et al. Factors affecting evidence-use in food policy-making processes in health and agriculture in Fiji. *BMC Pub Health*. 2017; 17: 1-10.
- Waqa G, Moodie M, Schultz J, et al. Process evaluation of a community-based intervention program: Healthy Youth Healthy Communities, an

- adolescent obesity prevention project in Fiji. *Glob Health Promot*. 2014; 20: 23-34.
- Wiseman V, Lagarde M, Batura N, et al. Measuring inequalities in the distribution of the Fiji Health Workforce. *Int J Equity Health*. 2017; 16: 1-8.
- Witter T, Poudevigne M, Lambrick DM, et al. A conceptual framework for managing modifiable risk factors for cardiovascular diseases in Fiji. *Perspect Public Health*. 2015; 135: 75-84.
- World Health Organization. Fiji Non-Communicable Diseases (NCD) Steps Survey 2002. Fiji: World Health Organization; 2002.
- World Health Organization. Western pacific country health information profiles: 2010 revision. Vietnam: World Health Organization Regional Office for the Western Pacific; 2010.
- World Health Organization. WHO Country Cooperation Strategy for Fiji 2013-2017. Geneva, Switzerland: World Health Organization Press; 2012.
- World Health Organization. Towards Healthy Islands: Pacific Noncommunicable Disease. World Health Organization; 2013.
- World Health Organization. WHO report on the global tobacco epidemic 2017. World Health Organization; 2017. Available from: http://www.wpro.who.int/southpacific/pic_meeting/2013/documents/P_HMM_PIC10_3_NCD.pdf
- Wynn JB. Fiji [Internet]. [place unknown]: New Industries; [date unknown; cited 2019 June 11]. Available from: <https://education.stateuniversity.com/pages/466/Fiji.html>

Suki and Tobacco in Fiji

- British American Tobacco. Fiji Social Report 2005. Fiji: Bluebird Printery; 2005 August. P. 58.
- Chadda R, Sengupta S. Tobacco use by Indian adolescents. *Tob Induc Dis*. 2003; 1: 8.
- David AM, Lew R, Lyman AK, et al. Eliminating tobacco-related disparities among Pacific Islanders through leadership and capacity building: Promising practices and lessons learned. *Health Promot Pract*. 2013; 14: 1-13.
- Diospyros [Internet]. [place unknown]: Revolvvy; [date unknown]. Available from: <https://www.revolvvy.com/page/Diospyros?mt=1>
- Dougall J, Pace S. Blown away by the art of cigar making. 2018 Jun 25 [cited 2019 May 19]; Available from: <https://timesofmalta.com/articles/view/blown-away-by-the-art-of-cigar-making.682752>
- Fact sheet: Fiji [Internet]. [place unknown]: World Health Organization Western Pacific Region; [date unknown]. Available from: <https://www.who.int/tobacco/media/en/Fiji.pdf>
- Farm Consultancy Services. Child labour in Fiji's tobacco growing industry. Lautoka, Fiji: Farm Consultancy Services; 2004.
- Foreign Trade of Fiji of NCE rolled tobacco - cigars, cheroots, cigarillos and cigarettes, of tobacco or of tobacco substitutes: [Internet]. [cited 2019

- Aug 5]. Available from: <https://trade.nosis.com/en/Comex/Import-Export/Fiji/rolled-tobacco--cigars-cheroots-cigarillos-and-cigarettes-of-tobacco-or-of-tobacco-substitutes/FJ/2402>
- Fowles J. Mainstream Smoke Emissions from 'Roll-your-own' Loose-leaf Tobacco Sold in New Zealand. A report for the Ministry of Health including an Appendix Report by the US Centers for Disease Control and Prevention. [internet] New Zealand: Institute of Environmental Science and Research Limited ("ESR"), 2008. [date unknown; cited 11 June 2019]. Available from: [http://www.moh.govt.nz/notebook/nbbooks.nsf/o/E3D5FCFB9D06CE07CC25750600071BE8/\\$file/smoke-emissions-rollyourown.pdf](http://www.moh.govt.nz/notebook/nbbooks.nsf/o/E3D5FCFB9D06CE07CC25750600071BE8/$file/smoke-emissions-rollyourown.pdf)
- GBD 2015 Tobacco Collaborators. Smoking prevalence and attributable disease burden in 195 countries and territories, 1990-2015: A systematic analysis from the Global Burden of Disease Study 2015. *The Lancet*. 2017; 389: 1885-906.
- Glover M, Nosa V, Watson D, et al. WhyKwit: A qualitative study of what motivates Maori, Pacific Island and low socio-economic peoples in Aotearoa/ New Zealand to stop smoking. Auckland: University of Auckland, School of Population Health, Centre for Tobacco Control Research.
- Gokhale BG. Tobacco in Seventeenth-Century India. *Agr Hist*. 1974; 48: 484-92.
- ICAR – Central Tobacco Research Institute. Origin of the Crop [Internet]. Andhra Pradesh, India: ICAR – Central Tobacco Research Institute; [date unknown]. Available from: https://ctri.icar.gov.in/for_origin.php
- Ikisan. Tobacco [Internet]. Ikisan. [cited 2019 May 19]. Available from: <http://www.ikisan.com/tg-tobacco-morphology.html>
- Issues in the global tobacco economy. Rome: Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations FAO, Communication Division; 2003.
- Jani D, Binorkar S. Traditional Medicinal Usage of Tobacco and #8211; A Review. *Spatula DD*. 2012; 2: 127.
- Karalus LE, Binoka DT, Karalus N. Knowledge, Attitudes, Behaviour and Needs of Pacific People on Tobacco Smoking and Quitting. Wellington, NZ: Ministry of Health; 2010.
- Kishore K. Monograph of Tobacco (*Nicotiana Tabacum*). *Indian Journal of Drugs*. 2014; 2: 5–23.
- Kumar A. 'Young Adults Make Up Highest Number Of Smokers In Fiji.' 2017 Jun 1 [cited 2019 May 19]; Available from: <https://fjjsun.com.fj/2017/06/01/young-adults-make-up-highest-number-of-smokers-in-fiji/>
- Lal P. Bidi – A short history. *Curr Sci*. 2009; 96: 1335-7.
- López-Giraldo A, Cruz A, Molins L, et al. Characterization, localization and comparison of c-Kit+ lung cells in never smokers and smokers with and without COPD. *BMC Pulm Med*. 2018; 18: 1-7.
- Marshall M. The second fatal impact: cigarette smoking, chronic disease, and the epidemiological transition in Oceania. *Soc Sci Med*. 1991; 33: 1327-42.
- Me N. Will the cheroot tradition go up in smoke? 2017 Aug 10 [cited 2019 May 19]; Available from: <https://www.mmtimes.com/lifestyle/27203-will-the-cheroot-tradition-go-up-in-smoke.html>

- Meo L, Phillips D, Brough R. Smoking in Viti Levu, Fiji. *Pac Health Dialog*. [year unknown]; 3: 41-2.
- Origin and Development of India's Tobacco Industry. In *India*; [cited 2019 May 19]. p. 42–81. Available from: https://shodhganga.inflibnet.ac.in/bitstream/10603/143158/11/11_chapter%203.pdf
- Parham RHB. Fiji Plants, their Names and Uses. *J Polyn Soc*. 1941; 50: 81-96.
- Prasad VM. Case study of tobacco cultivation and alternate crops in India [Internet]. World Health Organization; 2007 [cited 2019 Feb 6]. Available from: https://www.who.int/tobacco/framework/cop/events/2007/india_case_study.pdf
- Puamau ES, Roberts G, Schmich L, et al. Drug and Alcohol Use in Fiji: A Review. *Pac Health Dialog*. 2011; 17: 165-72.
- Singh B, Matsuba T. Prevalence of tobacco use in Fiji. *Pac Health Dialog*. [year unknown]; 6: 178-82.
- Singh S. Register, Tobacco Retailers Urged. *Mailife*. 2014 Nov 16. Available from: <https://www.mailife.com.fj/register-tobacco-retailers-urged/>
- Squared P. Suki Production [Internet]. Fiji; 2018 [cited 2019 May 19]. Available from: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=VnAU8neEkhM>
- Talei F. 5000 Tobacco, Suki Sellers Get Legal. *Fiji Sun*. 2012 Jun 28: 1.
- Tamil Cricket Channel. Surutu Cigar Making process in Village | How To Make Surutu or Cigar [Internet]. 2017 [cited 2019 May 19]. Available from: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ugo7BPEPd-I>
- The Global Youth Tobacco Survey Collaborative Group. Tobacco use among youth: A cross country comparison. *Tob Con*. 2002; 11: 252-70.
- The history of tobacco in India and its value in society today [Internet]. [cited 2019 Aug 5]. Available from: <http://globalhealthequality.blogspot.com/2011/11/history-of-tobacco-in-india-and-its.html>
- The Irrawaddy. Cigars and Cheroots. 1999 Feb [cited 2019 May 19]; 7(2). Available from: https://www2.irrawaddy.com/article.php?art_id=1041
- The Tobacco Atlas. Fiji Country Factsheet: Issues. Fiji: The Tobacco Atlas; [date unknown].
- The Tobacco Institute of India. Tobacco Production [Internet]. Nehru Place, New Delhi: The Tobacco Institute of India; [date unknown]. Available from: <https://www.tiionline.org/facts-sheets/tobacco-production/>
- Tobacco [Internet]. *Nicotiana Rustica*. [cited 2019 May 19]. Available from: <https://www.nicotianarustica.org/tobacco>
- Tobacco Atlas. Fiji [Internet]. 2019 [cited 2019 June 10]. Available from: <https://tobaccoatlas.org/country/fiji/>
- Trichinopoly cigar [Internet]. [place unknown]: Revolvvy; [date unknown]. Available from: <https://www.revolvvy.com/page/Trichinopoly-cigar>
- Tuomilehto J, Zimmet P, Taylor R, et al. Smoking rates in Pacific islands. *Bull World Health Organ*. 1986; 64: 447-56.

- Waqa G, McCool J, Snowdon W, et al. Adolescents Perceptions of Pro- and Antitobacco Imagery and Marketing: Qualitative Study of Students from Suva, Fiji. *Biomed Res Int.* 2015; 2015: 1-7.
- Young J. The History of Tobacco and Its Growth Throughout the World [Internet]. [place unknown]: Stanford; [date unknown]. Available from: https://web.stanford.edu/class/e297c/trade_environment/health/tobacco.html

Kava

- Alcohol and Drug Foundation. Kava [Internet]. Alcohol and Drug Foundation. 2019 [cited 2019 Aug 5]. Available from: <https://adf.org.au/drug-facts/kava/>
- Aporosa S. Yaqona (Kava) as a Symbol of Cultural Identity. *Locale: The Australasian Pacific Journal of Regional Food Studies.* 2014; 4: 79-101.
- Aporosa SA. Kava and Ethno-cultural Identity in Oceania. In: *The Palgrave handbook of ethnicity.* Singapore: Springer Nature; 2019.
- Cairney S, Maruff P, Clough AR. The neurobehavioural effects of kava. *Aust N Z J Psychiat.* 2002; 36: 657-62.
- Cairney S, Clough AR, Maruff P, et al. Saccade and Cognitive Function in Chronic Kava User. *Neuropsychopharmacol.* 2003; 28: 389-96.
- Clough A. Health Effects of Heavy Kava Use in Indigenous Australians [PhD thesis]. Australia: Northern Territory University; 2003.
- Food Standards Australia New Zealand. Kava: A Human Health Risk Assessment. Technical Report Series No. 30, 2004. [internet] Canberra, ACT: Food Standards Australia New Zealand; 2005.
- Fu PP, Xia Q, Guo L, et al. Toxicity of Kava Kava. *J Environ Sci Health C Environ Carcinog Ecotoxicol Rev.* 2008; 26: 89-112.
- Kava: Uses, Side Effects, Interactions, Dosage, and Warning [Internet]. [cited 2019 May 19]. Available from: <https://www.webmd.com/vitamins/ai/ingredientmono-872/kava>
- Kava R. The adverse effects of kava. *Pac Health Dialog.* 2001; 8: 115-8.
- McDonald D, Jowitt A. Kava in the Pacific Islands: a contemporary drug of abuse? *Harm Reduction Digest* 9. *Drug Alcohol Rev.* 2000; 19: 227.
- Narayanapillai SC, Balbo S, Leitzman P, et al. Dihydropyridine from kava blocks tobacco carcinogen 4-(methylnitrosamino)-1(3-pyridyl)-1-butanone-induced lung tumorigenesis and differentially reduces DNA damage in A/J mice. *Carcinogenesis.* 2014; 35: 2365-72.
- Nerurkar PV, Dragull K, Tang CS. In vitro toxicity of kava alkaloid, pipermethystine, in HepG2 cells compared to kavalactones. *Toxicol Sci.* 2004; 79: 106-11.
- Nosa V, Ofanoa M. The Social, cultural and medicinal use of Kava for Twelve Tongan born men living in Auckland, New Zealand. *Pac Health Dialog.* 2009; 15: 96-102.
- Sarris J, Stough C, Teschke R, et al. Kava for the Treatment of Generalized Anxiety Disorder RCT: Analysis of Adverse Reactions, Liver Function, Addiction, and Sexual Effects. *Phytother Res.* 2013; 27: 1723-8.

- Singh YN, Blumenthal M. Kava: An overview. American Botanical Council. 1997; 33: 33.
- Taufa N, Nosa V. Her Side of the Kava Story. Lecture presented at; 2015; Counties Manukau.
- The Truth About Kava in Fiji [Internet]. Why Wait to See the World? 2012 [cited 2019 Aug 5]. Available from: <https://whywaittoseetheworld.com/truth-kava-in-fiji/>
- Thompson R, Ruch W, Hasenöhrl RU. Enhanced cognitive performance and cheerful mood by standardized extracts of Piper methysticum (Kava-kava). Hum Psychopharmacol Clin Exp. 2004; 19: 243-50.
- Tomlinson M. A Consuming Tradition: Kava drinking in Fiji. Expedition. 2006; 48: 8-17.
- Where Did Kava Originate? [Internet]. Kava.Guru. 2013 [cited 2019 Aug 5]. Available from: <http://kava.guru/ask-kava-guru/true-origin-of-kava/>
- Xiaolin Z, Simoneau AR. Flavokawain A, a Novel Chalcone from Kava Extract, Induces Apoptosis in Bladder Cancer Cells by Involvement of Bax Protein-Dependent and Mitochondria-Dependent Apoptotic Pathway and Suppresses Tumor Growth in Mice. Cancer Res. 2005; 65: 3479-86.

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- Abrams D, Monti P, Carey K, et al. Reactivity to smoking cues and relapse: Two studies of discriminant validity. Behav Res Ther. 1988; 26: 225-33.
- Ali N, Chand D, Bonnar M, et al. Strengthening Tobacco Control Enforcement in Fiji. Fiji Journal of Public Health. 2017; 6: 29.
- Brownson R, Hopkins D, Wakefield M. Effects of smoking restrictions in the workplace. Annu Rev Public Health. 2002; 23: 333-48.
- DeCorby-Watson K, Mensah G, Bergeron K, et al. Effectiveness of capacity building interventions relevant to public health practice: A systematic review. BMC Public Health. 2018; 18: 1-15.
- DiGiacomo M, Davidson PM, Abbott PA, et al. Smoking Cessation in Indigenous Populations of Australia, New Zealand, Canada and the United States: Elements of Effective Interventions. Int J Environ Res Public Health. 2011; 8: 388-410.
- Gouda HN, Richards NC, Beaglehole R, et al. Health information priorities for more effective implementation and monitoring of non-communicable disease programs in low- and middle-income countries: Lessons from the Pacific. BMC Med. 2015; 13: 1-8.
- Groth-Marnat G, Leslie S, Renneker M. Tobacco Control in a Traditional Fijian Village: Indigenous Methods of Smoking Cessation and Relapse Prevention. Soc Sci Med. 1996; 43: 473-477.
- Linhart C, Naseri T, Lin S, et al. Tobacco smoking trends in Samoa over four decades: can continued globalization rectify that which it has wrought? Global Health. 2017; 13: 31.
- Mauri Ora Associates, Medical Council of New Zealand. Best health outcomes for Pacific Peoples: Practice implications. Wellington: Medical Council of New Zealand; 2010.

- Stebbins KR. Transnational tobacco companies and health in underdeveloped countries: Recommendations for avoiding a smoking epidemic. Soc Sci Med. 1990; 30: 227-35.
- Talei F. 5000 tobacco, suki sellers get legal. Fiji Sun [Internet]. 2012 June 28 [cited 2019 June 10]. Available from: <https://fijisun.com.fj/2012/06/28/5000-tobacco-suki-sellers-get-legal/>
- Tobacco Control Laws. Legislation by Country: Fiji [Internet]. Tobacco Control Laws. 2019 [cited 2019 May 19]. Available from: <https://www.tobaccocontrolaws.org/legislation/country/fiji/summary>
- Tobacco Free Pacific Network 2025, World Health Organization Western Pacific Region. Tobacco Free Pacific 2025: Tobacco use fuels the Pacific NCD crisis. [place unknown]: World Health Organization Western Pacific Region; [date unknown].
- World Health Organization Western Pacific Region. Case Study: Implementing regulatory measures for tobacco control in Fiji [Internet]. [place unknown]: [date unknown]. Available from: <http://www.uhcwpr.info/quality/case-studies/case-study-implementing-regulatory-measures-for-tobacco-control-in-fiji/>